

COMPARISON OF NOTCH EFFECTS ON STRENGTH OF LAMINATE AND WOVEN COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Tensile tests on glass/epoxy composites containing circular holes were conducted. Hole size effect on the strength of the composites was investigated. Two reinforcing types(woven plates and flat laminates) and two laminating sequence(cross-ply and angle-ply) were investigated. For each test, five different sizes of hole diameter were employed. Whitney's and Pipes' failure criteria were considered in strength analysis. Since a larger hole size induces broader stress concentration, a modification was introduced characteristic length as a function of hole radius. This modified criteria closely estimates the experimental data. Fracture mode is also investigated. In flat laminates, delamination was related ; In angle-ply laminates, matrix shear failure was occurred.

KEYWORDS : Notch ; Strength ; Failure Criterion ; Laminate ; Woven

1. INTRODUCTION

The purpose of a joint is to transfer loads from one part to another in a structure. For composites structures, the basic joining methods are mechanical and bonded joints. Mechanical joints permit quick disassembly for repair, no surface preparation, easy to inspect for joint quality but causing highly localized stress concentration around the joint, adding weight to the structure and possible corrosion problem. Bonded joints may distribute the load over a larger area than mechanical joints, require no holes, but difficult to disassemble without either destroying or damaging the substrates, difficult to inspect for joint quality and may be affected by service temperature, humidity and other environmental conditions. Mechanical joints need holes which give rise to local strength degradation by stress concentration. There have been some models for predicting notched strength of composites[1-3]. In this paper, notched strength of glass/epoxy laminates and woven composites are studied experimentally and analytically. The investigated stacking sequence of the laminates were $[0/90]_2$ cross-ply and $[+45/-45]_2$ angle ply. The effect of hole size is examined using five different size of hole radius. To predict the influence of hole size on the notched strength, a modification on Whitney's failure criterion is made. Failure modes of notched laminate and woven composites are also investigated through scanning electron microscopic analysis.

2. THEORETICAL APPROACH

2.1 WN(Whitney and Nuismer) Model Whitney and Nuismer proposed two criteria for predicting notched strength of the composite materials containing circular holes or cracks [1]. These failure criteria are the point stress criterion and the average stress criterion. They assumed that fracture occurs when the stress at some distance away from the hole reaches the unnotched strength. Point stress criterion is assumed that failure occurs when the stress, σ_y , over a distance, p , away from the hole is equal to the unnotched strength ;

$$\sigma_y(r + p, 0) = \sigma_0 \quad (1)$$

Average stress criterion is assumed that failure occurs when the average stress, σ_y , over a distance, a , away from the hole is equal to the unnotched strength ;

$$\frac{1}{a} \int_r^{r+a} \sigma_y(x, 0) dx = \sigma_0 \quad (2)$$

where p or a is the characteristic length in each failure criterion. For an infinite orthotropic plate containing a circular hole of radius r , the stress along the x -axis can be expressed by [4] ;

$$\sigma_y(x, 0) = \frac{\sigma_0^\infty}{2} \left\{ 2 + \left(\frac{r}{x}\right)^2 + 3\left(\frac{r}{x}\right)^4 - (K_T^\infty - 3) \left[5\left(\frac{r}{x}\right)^6 - 7\left(\frac{r}{x}\right)^8 \right] \right\} \quad (3)$$

where, K_T^∞ : the stress concentration factor for an infinite plate [5]

$$K_T^\infty = 1 + \left\{ \frac{2}{A_{22}} \left(\sqrt{A_{11}A_{22}} - A_{12} + \frac{A_{11}A_{22} - A_{12}^2}{2A_{66}} \right) \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (4)$$

where, A_{ij} : orthotropic in-plane stiffness

And in terms of effective moduli,

$$K_T^\infty = 1 + \left\{ 2 \left[\frac{E_y}{E_x} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} - \nu_{yx} \right\} + E_y / G_{yx} \quad (5)$$

where, E_x, E_y : effective modulus of laminate
in the x and y directions, respectively
 E_{yx} : effective shear modulus of laminate
 ν_{yx} : effective Poisson's ratio

In case of point stress criterion, strength ratio can be expressed in terms of radius and the characteristic length from the equations (1) and (3) ;

$$\frac{\sigma_N^\infty}{\sigma_0} = \frac{2}{\left\{ 2 + \xi_1^2 + 3\xi_1^4 - (K_T^\infty - 3) (5\xi_1^6 - 7\xi_1^8) \right\}} \quad (6)$$

where, $\xi_1 = \frac{r}{r+p}$

While, in case of average stress criterion, strength ratio can be expressed in terms of radius and the characteristic length from the equation (2) and (3) ;

$$\frac{\sigma_N^\infty}{\sigma_0} = \frac{2(1 - \xi_2)}{\{2 - \xi_2^2 - \xi_2^4 + (K_T^\infty - 3)(\xi_2^6 - \xi_2^8)\}} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{where, } \xi_2 = \frac{r}{r+a}$$

Whitney assumed that the characteristic lengths are not concerned with hole size. Therefore the characteristic length is a function of consisting material, reinforcing type and loading direction. When the characteristic length is independent of hole radius, accurate strength prediction can be achieved using Whitney's prediction method. However, according to some experimental results with various material and stacking sequence, characteristic length is not a constant but a function of hole size [2, 6]. The above equations involved in stress distribution of infinite plate. However, some correction should be made since the specimen has finite width. This point could be solved by introducing finite width correction factor, Y which relates the strength of finite plate with that of infinite plate as follows ;

$$\sigma_N^\infty = Y \sigma_N \quad (8)$$

where, σ_N : notched strength of real plate

For the isotropic material, finite width correction factor is expressed as follows [7] ;

$$Y = \frac{2 + (1 - 2r/w)^3}{3(1 - 2r/w)} \quad (9)$$

where, w : specimen width

When the length of the specimen is long, orthotropic finite width correction factor is approaches to isotropic finite width correction factor. Mar demonstrated that as long as the length-to-width ratio of the specimen is larger than 3, the error between isotropic and orthotropic finite width correction factor is less than 2% [8]. In this case, there is only small error on the strength.

2.2 PWG(Pipes, Wetherhold and Gillespie) Model Pipes, Wetherhold and Gillespie assumed that the characteristic length of the point stress criterion is an exponential function of hole size [3] ;

$$p = \frac{1}{c_0} \left(\frac{r}{r_0} \right)^m \quad (10)$$

where, c_0 : notch sensitivity factor
 r_0 : reference notch radius
 m : exponential parameter

$$\frac{\sigma_N^\infty}{\sigma_o} = \frac{2}{\{ 2 + \lambda^2 + 3\lambda^4 - (K_T^\infty - 3) (5\lambda^6 - 7\lambda^8) \}} \quad (11)$$

$$\text{where, } \lambda = \frac{1}{1 + r^{m-1} r_o^{-m} c_o^{-1}}$$

Since σ_o , m and c_o can be measured from the experiments, notched strength can be expressed as a function of hole size only. Generally, exponential parameter is located in the region of $0 < m < 1$. For the case of $m < 0$, the characteristic length does not defined at the point of $r = 0$. When $m = 0$ this model has the same meaning of WN model, and when $m = 1$, notched strength is independent of hole size. The parameters m and c_o can be determined from experimental data by least squares fit.

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Both flat and woven glass/epoxy composites manufactured by Han Kuk Fiber Glass Company were used in this study. Fiber volume fraction (V_f) of flat laminates was 60% while that of woven composites was 62%. The woven laminates have 11 woven roving with thickness of 2.2 mm and the thickness of flat laminates was 3.5 mm. Two types of stacking sequence were investigated for both flat and woven laminates. Flat laminates were cross-ply, $[0/90]_{2s}$ and angle-ply, $[\pm 45/-45]_{2s}$ while woven laminates were cross-ply and angle-ply which has a 45 degree fiber orientation from cross-ply. Gauge length and width of the specimen were 150 and 20 mm, respectively as shown in Figure 1. A circular hole was made at the center of the specimen by a drilling machine at a speed of 920 rpm. Five different hole, radii, 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 mm, were chosen to analyze hole size effect and 3 specimens were tested at each point. A UTM Autograph was used for static testing. Load was monitored by a load cell and load and strain were recorded by an X-Y recorder. The strength measurements were conducted at a displacement rate of 1 mm/min and 2 mm/min for cross-ply and angle-ply laminates, respectively. Scanning electron microscopic examination of fracture surfaces was studied. A thin (10 to 20 nm) gold coating was deposited to reduce charging.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The characteristic length calculated by equations (7) and (9) can be expressed ;

$$\frac{\sigma_N}{\sigma_o} = \frac{2}{\{ 2 + \xi_1^2 + 3\xi_1^4 - (K_T^\infty - 3) (5\xi_1^6 - 7\xi_1^8) \}} \frac{3 (1 - 2r/w)}{\{ 2 + (1 - 2r/w)^3 \}} \quad (12)$$

The unnotched strength, σ_o , notched strength, σ_N and stress concentration factor, K_T^∞ were obtained from the experiments. Hence the above equation is a function of characteristic length only. It is found that characteristic length of three laminates increases as hole radius increases except in case of angle-ply flat laminates as shown in Figure 2. The experimental results suggested that the behavior of characteristic length could be strongly influenced by stacking sequence. The WN model assumed constant characteristic length which is quite different from our experimental results. Therefore, it seems that general polynomial might be better than WN

model and simple exponential model(PWG model) in the analysis of characteristic length. The polynomial can be expressed as follows ;

$$p = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} p_i r^i = p_0 + p_1 r + p_2 r^2 + p_3 r^3 + \dots \quad (13)$$

where, p_i : constant

The above polynomial could be represented the general behavior of characteristic length. However, the use of the above equation might require a lot of experimental data and have some difficulties in employed. After a close examination of experimental data, we propose a simple linear HK model by neglecting non-linear higher order terms. It should be pointed out that proposed model is a starting attempt to evaluate behavior of characteristic length of glass/epoxy composite laminate. The fracture models investigated in this study can be expressed as follows;

$$\text{WN model} \quad p = \text{const.} \quad (14.a)$$

$$\text{HK model} \quad p = p_0 + p_1 r \quad (14.b)$$

$$\text{PWG model} \quad p = c r^m \quad (14.c)$$

where, p_0, p_1, c and m : constants

Stress concentration factor (K_T^∞) and strength ratio were calculated from the experimental data. The linear least squares method is used to evaluate parameters of fracture models. The evaluation results are presented in Table 1. The experimental data and calculated values are compared in Figure 2. The comparison results show that PWG model and proposed HK model have good agreements with experimental data. As mentioned earlier, the behavior of characteristic length of angle-ply flat laminate is quite different from the other laminates. In this particular case, PWG and HK models predict that the characteristic length decreases as hole radius increases. This prediction is just the opposite to the other cases. It is also found that the characteristic length of cross-ply was less than that of angle-ply. This implies that notch effect of cross-ply laminates is greater than that of angle-ply.

The evaluations of SSR are given in Table 3. The comparison results show that HK model and PWG model seem to predict notched strength of glass/epoxy laminates well. It is found that notched strength of angle-ply flat laminate decreases linearly with increasing hole radius. While, in case of the other three laminates, the strength decreases rapidly at the small radius region.

The experimental data of unnotched and notched specimens are presented in Table 2. The strength ratios of unnotched specimens to notched specimens are shown in Figure 3. The comparison between predicted value and experimental data is also presented. Finite correction factor is used in the strength prediction. In addition to the Figure 3, the residual sum of squares(SSR) of the observed and predicted strength ratios would give brief over all comparison through the SSR alone could not determine the superiority of fracture models. The SSR for the strength could be expressed as follows;

$$\text{SSR} = \sum_{i=1}^n (\sigma_{\text{exp}} - \sigma_{\text{pred}})^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_{\text{err}}^2 \quad (15)$$

where, σ_{exp} : experimental data
 σ_{pred} : predicted strength
 σ_{err} : error between experimental and predicted strength

Scanning electron micrographs of fracture surfaces are presented in Figure 4-7. Figure 4 shows the fracture characteristics of the cross-ply, $[0/90]_2$ flat laminates. Fiber pull-out and fiber-matrix debonding in transverse direction are shown in Figure 4 (a). Fiber break and brittle fiber fracture are shown in Figure 4 (b). The fractography of the angle-ply, $[+45/-45]_2$ flat laminates are shown in Figure 5. Delamination surface is shown in Figure 5 (a). The major features of Figure 5 (b) are clean fibers, which indicates fiber-matrix debonding, and matrix microcracks which are caused by shear force. A typical fractography of cross-ply woven laminates are shown in Figure 6. Figure 6 (b) shows tensile resin fracture, broken fibers and fiber pull-out. Fracture surface of angle-ply woven laminates can be seen in Figure 7. This figure shows matrix residue on fiber surface, hackle markings and fiber break which cannot be observed in angle-ply flat laminates.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Notch effect of glass/epoxy flat and woven laminates can be characterized by WN model. However, characteristic length of glass/epoxy composites is not constant but a linear function of hole radius which is quite different from Whitney and Nuismer's results. It is found that proposed linear fracture model predicts unnotch strength better than WN model and PWG model.

Fractography shows the complicated failure mechanism of glass/epoxy notched composites. Fiber break, fiber pull-out and debonding are major failure modes in cross-ply while major failure modes of angle-ply flat laminates are delamination and matrix shear failure. In the Failure mode, delamination occur in flat laminates, failure occurs without delamination in woven laminates, fiber breakage in cross-ply and resin failure by shear force in angle-ply.

REFERENCES

1. R. J. Nuismer and J. M. Whitney, Fracture Mechanics of Composites, ASTM STP 593, American Society of Testing and Materials, 1975, pp. 117-142.
2. R. F. Karlak, Proceedings of Failure Modes in Composites /IV, The Metallurgical Society of AIME, Chicago, 1977, pp. 105-117.
3. R. B. Pipes, R. C. Wetherhold, and J. W. Gillespie Jr., Journal of Composite Materials, 12, 148 (1979).
4. H. J. Konish, and J. M. J. M. Whitney, Journal of Composite Materials, 9, 157 (1975).
5. S. G. Lekhnitskii, Anisotropic Plates, Science Publishers Inc., New York, 1968.
6. J. M. Whitney, and R. Y. Kim, "Effect of Stacking Sequence on the Notched Strength of Composite Laminates in AFMLTR - 76 - 177", 1977.
7. R. E. Peterson, Stress Concentration Factors, John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1974.
8. J. Mar, Mechanics of Composite Review, Air Force Materials Laboratory and Air Force Office of Scientific Research Technical Report, 1976, pp. 117-122.

TABLE 1 Characteristic lengths of the three models

(unit : mm)

specimen \ model	WN model	HK model	PWG model
cross-ply flat	0.980	$0.540 + 0.146 r$	$0.638 r^{0.407}$
angle-ply flat	1.718	$1.843 - 0.042 r$	$1.772 r^{-0.039}$
cross-ply woven	0.912	$0.302 + 0.203 r$	$0.506 r^{0.558}$
angle-ply woven	1.317	$0.448 + 0.290 r$	$0.720 r^{0.573}$

TABLE 2 Strength Data

(MPa)

spec. \ r	0 mm	1 mm	2 mm	3 mm	4 mm	5 mm
cross-ply flat	429.1	333.2	294.7	241.5	196.7	175.0
	417.2	308.7	266.0	214.9	191.1	155.4
	407.4	291.2	247.1	210.0	188.3	147.7
angle-ply flat	133.0	117.6	101.5	85.4	66.5	49.7
	128.1	116.9	94.5	79.8	65.1	49.0
	127.4	114.8	94.5	78.4	60.9	49.0
cross-ply flat	265.0	174.8	144.8	124.7	113.6	100.2
	252.9	171.5	143.7	123.6	110.7	93.5
	226.1	168.2	142.5	120.3	109.1	92.4
angle-ply flat	153.7	111.4	95.8	84.6	72.4	66.8
	151.5	111.4	94.7	82.4	72.4	61.2
	147.0	109.1	92.4	81.3	71.3	59.0

TABLE 3 Errors in normalized strength by SSR

specimen \ model	WN model	HK model	PWG model
cross-ply flat	4.70×10^{-2}	1.92×10^{-2}	1.83×10^{-2}
angle-ply flat	0.71×10^{-2}	0.68×10^{-2}	0.72×10^{-2}
cross-ply woven	6.11×10^{-2}	0.26×10^{-2}	0.38×10^{-2}
angle-ply woven	6.83×10^{-2}	0.23×10^{-2}	0.28×10^{-2}

FIGURE 1. Configuration of the Specimen

(a) cross-ply flat laminate

(b) angle-ply flat laminate

(c) cross-ply woven composite

(d) angle-ply woven composite

FIGURE 2. Characteristic lengths versus hole radius

(a) cross-ply flat laminate

(b) angle-ply flat laminate

(c) cross-ply woven composite

(d) angle-ply woven composite

FIGURE 3. Strength ratios for real plates

FIGURE 4. SEM fractograph of cross-ply flat laminate

FIGURE 5. SEM fractograph of angle-ply flat laminate

FIGURE 6. SEM fractograph of cross-ply woven composite

FIGURE 7. SEM fractograph of angle-ply woven composite